

HIGH STRENGTH MULTIFUNCTIONAL STRUCTURAL BATTERY BASED ON SOLID-STATE G-CNT CARBON FIBER HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Commercially available PAN-based carbon fibers have a great potential of load-bearing electrodes and multifunctional battery applications which combine solid polymer electrolyte with carbon fiber hybrid composites. As a system level approach to aerospace application for a novel multifunctional structure-battery and its electrodes, three-phase carbonaceous materials were synthesized for one hybrid composites. Two types of surface modified carbon fabrics – a G-CNT carbon fabric and a CNT carbon fabric – were designed and fabricated with the pristine carbon fabric as a reference. The G-CNT(Graphene-CNT) carbon fabric was fabricated by synthesizing graphene layers on carbon fiber woven fabric surface and grafting CNT thereafter. The CNT carbon fabric was manufactured by grafting CNT forest on the surface of carbon fabric. The designed porous-nano carbon fabric electrodes have shown good electrical characteristic, especially the G-CNT Carbon electrode showed high electrical conductivity since it has good electrical and mechanical contact. The extended application as the structure-battery can have good electrical performance in terms of the specific energy and the specific capacity. The electrical capacity was evaluated for free-standing electrodes comprised of the G-CNT and the CNT-grafted carbon fabric anodes with a Li-metal cathode as the counter electrode in two electrode system.

High strength multifunctional structural battery based on solid-state G-CNT carbon fiber hybrid composites was successfully fabricated and experimented for electrical and structural study. Multilayered G-CNT carbon fabric electrode had the lowest electrical resistance and the highest conductivity. In mechanical properties by tensile loading, the G-CNT carbon fabric electrode had high strength retention in a level of 92-95% of pristine carbon fabric. It can be highly competitive for the potential application of nanocomposite structure-battery electrode of multifunction.

Future work on these architectures can include the enhancement of G-CNT carbon fiber hybrid cell for the advanced layered structural batteries.

1. INTRODUCTIONS

The design requirements of carbon fiber hybrid composite electrodes are mechanically robust and electrically conductive ones for commercially available applications. G-CNT carbon fiber hybrid composite electrode is the one that is comprised of horizontally reinforcing graphene layers and Carbon Nanotube vertically aligned on the carbon fiber woven fabric. This concept of hybrid composite cell can improve the contact resistance in-between layers of carbon fibers, graphene layers, and CNT forest contacts with metallic nanoparticles as well.

Structural batteries function as a battery and a load bearing structural component simultaneously enhanced in mechanical and electrical properties. As a load-bearing multifunctional battery which combines solid polymer electrolyte with carbon fiber electrodes, Solid-State G-CNT carbon fiber hybrid composites were successfully fabricated and experimented. G-CNT-carbon fabric and CNT carbon fabric were synthesized by thermal CVD(Chemical Vapor Deposition) process for multifunctional characterization. The electrical conductivity and capacity for electrical characteristics and the tensile property for mechanical characteristics were evaluated. Specific resistance, electrical conductivity, specific capacity and mechanical strength were evaluated as the results.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Continuous carbon fiber based electrodes were used for the enhancement of electrical and mechanical contact. Commercially available PAN-based carbon fiber – TR30 manufactured by Mitsubishi Rayon – was used and its known mechanical properties are as follows:

Tensile Strength	Tensile Modulus	Density
4,354Mpa (444kgf/mm ²)	235GPa (24,000kgf/mm ²)	1.795g/cm ³

Table 1: Mechanical Properties of Commercially Available Carbon Fiber, TR30 (Mitsubishi Rayon)

The solid polymer electrolyte (SBS-g-POEM) synthesized in the lab scale combining with carbon fiber electrode was used. The ionic conductivity is 10^{-3} S/cm.

2.1. Synthesis of G-CNT and CNT Carbon Fiber

Structural batteries comprised of solid electrolyte and carbon fiber laminae have good mechanical properties with the sacrifice in the ionic conductivity. Electrical capacity needs to be enhanced in electrical conductivity without losing the load-bearing capability. Designed composite electrodes comprised of one-dimensional CNT and two-dimensional graphene which are basically allotrope materials synthesized by thermal CVD and three-dimensional carbon fiber woven fabric.

Two types of specimens – a G-CNT carbon fabric and a CNT carbon fabric – were prepared by synthesizing as following conditions:

Condition	Graphene-Growth	CNT-Growth
• Carbon Source (Gas)	C ₂ H ₂	CH ₄
• Flow Rate	1sccm	100sccm
• Time	5min.	10min.
• Temperature	960→840→800°C	600-700°C
• Carrier Gas	H ₂	H ₂ (Plasma Assistance)
• Power	50W	320W
• Time	5min.	10min.

Table 2: Growth Condition of G-CNT and CNT on Carbon Fabric by CVD Process

The G-CNT carbon fabric specimen was prepared by thermally depositing CNT bundle layers on Al buffer layer with Fe activating catalytic layer within 10nm-thick on the multiple layers of graphene. The multiple layers of graphene smaller than 20 layers were grown on 600nm-thick Ni nanoparticles on carbon fiber woven fabric. Another type – CNT grown carbon fabric(so-called hereafter “CNT carbon fabric”) – was prepared by thermally depositing CNT bundle layers on Al buffer layer with Fe activating catalytic layer within 10nm-thick on carbon fiber woven fabric [1]. As the third type of specimen, a pristine carbon fiber woven fabric was prepared to compare the behaviors of each cell with the behaviors of the carbon fabric surface modified before and after.

Figure 1 shows the fabrication scheme for the two types of surface modified carbon fabric. CNT electrode grown by the metallic catalyst on the carbon fabric (1) and Graphene-CNT electrode grown by the same condition of (1) after graphene grown under the preceding condition on carbon fabric (2) were prepared.

Figure 1: Scheme for the Two Types of Surface Modified Carbon Fabric

Figure 2 presents the surface morphology of carbon fabric electrode after CNT growth.

Figure 2: Carbon Fabric Surface Morphology after CNT growth

2.2. Measurement of Electrical Characteristics for Modified Carbon Fiber Unit Cell

In order to evaluate the electrical characteristics of the lamina as hybrid composite cell, it is required in the evaluation method that is in conformity with the standard test method. The fibrous composites are generally comprised of the fibers and polymer matrix which are characterized moderately conductive or insulating materials. However in this study, the electrical characteristics were evaluated for a layered electrode since conductive matrix would be applied to in-between lamina plies as an electrolyte. High temperature material characteristics are essentially required for aerospace application. Therefore, the correlation study between temperature and resistance was performed as a consideration of important factors for compatible utilization of G-CNT carbon fiber hybrid composite cell for structure-battery.

Fiber resistance and fabric resistivity information by the suppliers of commercially available carbon fibers and fabrics were provided by using their own methods [2]. We therefore utilized our own engineered test method basically referred to standard test methods that ensure even contact and consistent pressure to the samples [3]-[8]. Since the G-CNT carbon fabric and pristine carbon fabric laminas are thin within the thin film coverage and show the characteristics of low electrical resistance below 1Ω , the resistance of samples were measured using a manual probe station with Keithley 4200 based on the four-point probe method. To reduce the contact resistance between instrument and the sample, four electrically conductive metallic tips with flat square shape were contacted to prepared three types of sample. Three measurements in average were conducted at room temperature (23°C) for each sample to ensure the stable values of resistance under the operation of comprised system. To study the correlation between temperature and resistance, considered was following experimental setup shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Experimental Setup for Temperature and Resistance Measurements by Hot Chuck

Figure 3 shows the measurement system that enables the heating up by joule heating and collection of the temperature data using the thermocouples on the sample. The K-type thermocouples were used and tested initially and repetitively more than 3 times for verifying the reproducibility of temperature as they were attached on the sample. The insulating thin plate supported the sample fixed on the copper hot chuck which was ramped-up from -20 °C up to 100 °C.

The average values obtained through the four-point probe method were used to calculate the specific resistance (ρ) and electrical conductivity (σ) as follows:

$$\rho = \frac{1}{\sigma} = \frac{R \times A}{l} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

, where A is a cross sectional area, and l is a length of carbon fiber as measured samples.

2.3. Electrochemical Half Cell Test of Modified Carbon Fiber Electrode

G-CNT Carbon Fabric laminae electrode showed high electrical conductivity with good electrical and mechanical contact. Two types of specimens-G-CNT carbon fiber and CNT grown carbon fiber laminas-were synthesized by thermal CVD, and pristine carbon fiber laminas was prepared to test with these two types of specimen for electrochemical galvanostatic half-cell test. EC-Lab potentiostat/galvanostat was used for electrochemical half-cell test.

G-CNT and CNT carbon fabric electrodes were tested at free-standing after half-cell assembly. Experimental conditions are as follows:

Experimental Condition	
Counter Electrode (Cathode)	Li Metal (Ø16)
Working Electrode (Anode)	(Ø14)
Separator	Porous Glass Fabric
Electrolyte	1M LiPF ₆ EC/EMC=1:1 vol.
Test Cell Standard	2032 coin cell
Test Condition	250uA CC-CV, 2V, 100cycles

Table 3: Electrochemical Half Cell Test Condition

2.4. Tensile Properties Evaluation of Modified Carbon Fiber Unit Cell

The mechanical loading test using tensile specimens was conducted by using Instron 5583 universal testing machine system at room temperature(22 °C) and humidity of 50%. Maximum load is 2kN and strain rate is 0.020mm/mm. Fiber lamina and unit cell tensile tests were carried out by engineered method according to the standard ASTM C1557-14 [9]. In the designed and fabricated composite electrodes, tensile tests of lamina and unit cell using CNT carbon fabric were performed and compared with the pristine carbon fabric as a reference, since good electrical and mechanical contact was verified in preceding electrical measurement.

The purpose of this mechanical tensile test is first to understand the relationships between the mechanical properties of the microstructure and fracture processes. Second purpose is to ensure the potential capability using a load-bearing electrode and a structure-battery.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Electrical Characteristics

Three types of specimens – a G-CNT carbon fabric, a CNT carbon fabric and a pristine carbon fabric laminas – were measured to have good electrical characteristic of low electrical resistance below 1Ω, and the correlation between temperature and resistance was studied when the heat was ramped up from -20 °C up to 100 °C .

3.1.1 Electrical Characteristics of Pristine, CNT, and G-CNT Carbon Fabrics as Freestanding Electrode under the heat-up

Figure 4 shows that the electrical resistance of CNT carbon fabric is the highest in 3 types of specimen while a pristine carbon fabric is the lowest value among these specimens. The pristine carbon fabric indicates, when the temperature was ramped up from 0 °C to 100 °C, the resistance of the electrode increased monotonically with conductive behavior like metallic characteristics. However when the temperature ramped up from -20 °C up to 0 °C, the resistance of the carbon fabric decreased like semiconducting characteristics. The CNT carbon fabric specimen shows like semiconducting behavior in whole ranges of ramp-up. The G-CNT carbon fabric shows most stable behavior unaffected by temperature variation at least in the range of from -20 °C up to 100 °C. The G-CNT carbon fabric electrode could be speculated good mechanical contact with carbon fibers and vertically aligned CNTs in between.

Figure 4: Specific Resistance (left) and Electrical Conductivity (right) of G-CNT, CNT and Pristine Carbon Fabric Electrodes under Varying Temperature

Table 4 represents that the results of electrical characteristics which values are in average under varying temperature over -20°C up to 100°C.

Type of Electrode	Resistance (Ω)	Resistivity (Ω·cm)	Conductivity (S·cm)
Pristine Carbon Fabric	7.56×10^{-2}	8.32×10^{-2}	12.02
CNT Carbon Fabric	33.96×10^{-2}	37.36×10^{-2}	2.67
G-CNT Carbon Fabric	15.30×10^{-2}	16.83×10^{-2}	5.94

Table 4: Results of Electrical Characteristics by 4-point probe Measurement

3.2. Electrical Capacity

3.2.1 Electrochemical Characterization of CNT and G-CNT Carbon Fabric Electrodes as Half Cell

Type of Cell	G-CNT CWF	CNT-grafted CWF
Specific Capacity (mAh/g)	60mAh/g	140mAh/g

Table 5: Electrical Capacity by Li Half-Cell Test

Future work could be done by simultaneous electrochemical and mechanical loading setup for studying more practical load-bearing capability when the unit cell of layered structure is under various loading conditions.

3.3. Mechanical Properties

3.3.1 Tensile Strength Evaluation

Designed composite electrodes comprised of one-dimensional CNT, two-dimensional graphene and three-dimensional carbon fiber woven fabric were successfully synthesized and experimented for electrical study. Fabrication of the unit cell and the evaluation of mechanical properties by tensile loading were conducted to the advanced fabrication of layered structural batteries. Unit cell is the polymer electrolyte coated on the CNT carbon fabric.

Mechanical properties by tensile loading result that the tensile strength of the functionalized surface is 5-8% lower than that of no functionalized surface. Carbon fabric by tensile loading after modification of the fiber surface and coating of the polymer electrolyte had high strength retention in a level of 92-95% of pristine carbon fabric.

Type of Cell	Normalized Force	Strain (mm/mm)
Electrolyte coated Pristine Carbon Fabric	1	0.020
Electrolyte coated CNT Carbon Fabric Unit Cell -1 st	0.92	0.020
Electrolyte coated CNT Carbon Fabric Unit Cell -2 nd	0.95	0.020

Table 6: Mechanical Properties of Solid-State Pristine and CNT Carbon Fabric Unit Cell

The G-CNT carbon fiber hybrid composites were designed and characterized by fabricating graphene layers and grafting CNT on carbon fiber woven fabric surface. The designed porous-nano carbon composite electrodes showed good electrical and mechanical performance in multifunctional characteristics.

4. CONCLUSIONS

High strength multifunctional structural battery based on solid-state G-CNT carbon fiber hybrid composites was successfully fabricated and experimented for electrical and structural study. Multilayered G-CNT carbon fabric electrode had the lowest electrical resistance and the highest conductivity. In mechanical properties by tensile loading, the CNT carbon fabric had high strength retention in a level of 92-95% level of pristine carbon fabric. It can be highly competitive for the potential application of nanocomposite structure-battery electrode of multifunction.

Future work on these architectures can include the enhancement of G-CNT carbon fiber hybrid cell for advanced layered structural batteries. Hence, further correlation study of load bearing capability and faradic reaction as battery performance could be covered on trade-off matters between novel G-CNT carbon fiber hybrid electrodes and novel synthesized solid polymer electrolytes.

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